

Development of a Training Strategy for Consulting Sales Engineers in New Technologies for Business Solutions through Andragogy

Laura Ramírez P¹, Andres Ramirez-Portilla²

¹ Centro de Investigación Pedagógica del Caribe, Universidad Pedagógica del Caribe, S.C., Cancún, México

² Tecnológico de Monterrey, Escuela de Ingeniería y Ciencias, Ave. Eugenio Garza Sada 2501, Monterrey 64849, NL, Mexico

Email: ramirez.laura@gmail.com, ramirez.andres@tec.mx

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062607>

Abstract

This paper delves into the strategic development of a training program tailored to empower Sales Engineers engaged in consultative technology sales. The focus of this initiative lies in integrating and mastering New Technologies for Business Solutions, with a pedagogical emphasis on the application of Andragogy. Acknowledging the unique learning characteristics of adult professionals, this strategy aims to optimize the acquisition and utilization of knowledge in the rapidly evolving landscape of technology-driven business solutions. The foundation of the training strategy draws heavily from the principles of Andragogy, highlighting the importance of self-directed learning and the integration of adult learners' rich experiences in the educational process. Furthermore, the rapid instructional design principles are incorporated to ensure a targeted and practical approach to skill development in consultative technology sales. The training modules are designed to be dynamic and interactive, integrating real-world case studies and simulations that mirror the complexities of consultative technology sales. By emphasizing hands-on experiences and collaborative learning methodologies, the strategy aims to facilitate immediate knowledge application within the professional context. Evaluation mechanisms within the program assess the impact on sales performance and the adept utilization of New Technologies for Business Solutions. The continuous improvement cycle is driven by feedback mechanisms and performance metrics, ensuring the ongoing relevance and effectiveness of the Andragogy-based training strategy. This paper contributes to the intersection of adult learning, sales training, and technological solutions for businesses, offering practical insights into the successful implementation of Andragogy to enhance the competencies of Sales Engineers in navigating and capitalizing on the opportunities presented by new technologies in the realm of consultative sales.

Keywords: Andragogy; Training Strategy; Educational Innovation; Higher Education; Professional Education

1 Introduction

This work develops a practical case and explains the principle of andragogy applied to professional education, specifically, in the technological and business area. Normally industry and teaching are not fields that are consciously mixed, however, every time a person enters a new job position, they must have openness and enough humility to learn what they do not know and apply what they already understand. This combination of experience and innovation leads the new worker to face new challenges. These challenges are not only based on meeting the expectations of the position you obtained, but also on balancing your work and personal life or meeting goals, but at the same time you must learn an entire portfolio of new concepts and products within the company.

Taking a real example of Sales Engineers in New Technologies, several points that will be developed throughout this document must be considered. It begins by explaining what andragogy is and its principles; It is defined as the art and science of helping adults learn. According to him, andragogy is based on a series of principles that recognize the unique characteristics of adult learners, such as their autonomy, accumulated experience, intrinsic motivation and task orientation. This perspective implies a more student-centered approach, where learning is facilitated through active participation, the relevance of content and the practical application of knowledge (Knowles, 1984).

This work develops a practical case and explains the principle of andragogy applied to the technological and business field. Normally, industry and education are not fields that are consciously mixed, but each time a person enters a new job position, he must have openness and enough humility to learn what he does not know and apply what he already understands; this combination of experience and innovation leads the new worker to face new challenges. These challenges are not only based on fulfilling the expectations of the position you have been given, but also on balancing your work and personal life or achieving goals, while at the same time learning a whole portfolio of new concepts and products within the company.

Taking a real example of Sales Engineers in New Technologies, several points need to be considered that will be developed throughout this document. Firstly, it explains what andragogy is and its principles; it is defined as the art and science of helping adults learn. According to him, andragogy is based on a set of principles that recognize the unique characteristics of adult learners, such as their autonomy, accumulated experience, intrinsic motivation and task orientation. This perspective implies a more learner-centered approach where learning is facilitated through active participation, relevance of content and practical application of knowledge (Knowles, 1984). Merriam emphasizes the importance of recognizing the differences between adult learning and that of children. His concept of andragogy focuses on lifelong learning and the link between theory and practice. They argue that andragogy implies a participatory and collaborative approach where adults are seen as co-creators of knowledge and self-directed learning is encouraged. He also emphasizes the importance of reflection and dialogue in the adult learning process (Merriam & Bierema, 2014). Considering these two definitions, andragogy is considered essential to organize the knowledge of adults, it is the science that helps to develop the idea of learning and teaches us to know how adults learn, as they can decide autonomously what, how and when to learn. To better understand the concept, a comparison table between andragogy and pedagogy is shown.

Table 1. Comparing andragogy versus pedagogy

	Andragogy	Pedagogy
Definition	Art and science of helping adults learn, focusing on their autonomy, experience and intrinsic motivation (Knowles, 1984)	Educational approach focused on teaching children and adolescents, guided by an educator (Bruner, 1996)
Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-directed learning • Accumulated experience • Task orientation • Intrinsic motivation (Knowles, 1984) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educator-led instruction • Emphasis on discipline and structure • Development of cognitive and social skills (Bruner, 1996)
Approach	Participatory, collaborative and focused on the adult student (Merriam & Bierema, 2014)	Based on the authority of the educator and the transmission of knowledge (Bruner, 1996)

By understanding the six key principles of andragogy, we can build a strong foundation for designing effective adult learning programs and applying them in a variety of business settings. These principles emphasize learner autonomy, where adults take charge of their learning journey, driven by a desire to understand the benefits of acquiring new skills and knowledge (Knowles, 1984). Their extensive prior experience becomes a valuable resource (Knowles, 1984) and should be recognized in program design. Adults are most motivated by learning that directly addresses their job needs and helps them solve problems (Knowles, 1984). Intrinsic factors such as self-improvement and personal satisfaction drive their motivation more than external rewards (Knowles, 1984). Recognizing the diverse learning styles, experiences, and individual needs of adult learners is critical to effective teaching (Merriam & Bierema, 2014). Finally, real-life application and practical relevance are key to successful adult learning, as adults strive for continuous learning to reach their full potential (Merriam & Bierema, 2014).

2 Development

Based on this concept and principles then you can begin to think about what it takes to create an adult learning program, specifically for Consulting Sales Engineers in New Technologies. When you need to create a course with a specific structure, you must take into account the different phases that the content goes through until it is finished. The set of these phases is called instructional design. Getting involved in this process requires time, dedication, and effort from a team of professionals who cover different profiles within the company and who are willing to transmit their knowledge. Understand the concept of instructional design as the systematic and multidisciplinary process of planning, developing, evaluating, and managing effective and efficient educational solutions to achieve the objective of facilitating meaningful and lasting learning in students (Morrison, Ross & Kemp, 2013). Understanding the principles of adult learning (andragogy) provides the foundation for creating engaging and effective training programs for Consulting Sales Engineers (CSEs) in new technologies. Andragogy emphasizes learner autonomy, the use of prior experience, and a focus on practical application—all of which are critical for adult learners. However, creating a structured learning experience requires a systematic approach. This is where Instructional Design (ID) comes in. ID is the multi-step process of planning, developing, delivering, and evaluating instructional programs. It ensures efficient knowledge transfer and sustainable learning outcomes.

Although there are different approaches to train service engineer, it is common to see in industry six key steps that are used to create a structured approach for training continuous service engineers (CSEs) on new technologies. This approach aligns with the ASSURE model (Heinich 2002). It begins with a Needs Assessment, identifying the specific knowledge gaps and desired skills the CSEs need to acquire. Next, Design Objectives translate these needs into clear, measurable goals for the training program. Selecting Strategies focuses on choosing the most effective teaching methods, like interactive workshops or simulations, to achieve these objectives. Developing Materials involves creating engaging resources like e-learning modules or case studies, potentially leveraging existing corporate resources. Implementation and Delivery ensure effective program rollout, considering adult learning styles to foster a positive learning environment. Finally, Evaluation and Review emphasize ongoing assessment and feedback to improve the training program's effectiveness continuously. In this case, we planned to base the corporate training design on the ASSURE model.

The ASSURE model, developed by Heinich (2002), offers a structured yet flexible framework for crafting impactful learning experiences. This model, grounded in constructivism principles, prioritizes active student participation and the strategic use of technology. Imagine the ASSURE model as a roadmap, guiding instructional designers through a series of steps to ensure the creation of effective and engaging learning environments. The initial steps of the ASSURE model serve as a practical guide for successful learning. The first step, Analyze Learners, is all about getting to know the students. This involves identifying learner characteristics, needs, learning styles, and prior knowledge. By tailoring instruction to this specific audience, educators can ensure the content resonates with the students and lays a strong foundation for learning. Following this, the Establish Objectives step guides the development of clear and concise learning objectives.

These objectives outline the specific knowledge and skills students should gain from the instruction. Having a clear understanding of the desired outcomes allows educators to design the remaining steps of the model effectively. With a solid grasp of the learners and the desired learning outcomes, the ASSURE model begins crafting the actual learning experience. The Select Methods, Media, and Materials step involves choosing the most appropriate teaching strategies. This could include anything from lectures and discussions to simulations and games. Here, instructional designers select the most suitable technological resources and support materials to achieve the established objectives. The Utilize Media and Materials step focuses on seamlessly

integrating these chosen resources into the instructional design. This ensures alignment with goals, student needs, and the overall flow of the learning experience.

The ASSURE model is not a one-time solution but a dynamic process. The Require Learner Participation step emphasizes the importance of activities that actively engage students in the learning process. By fostering participation and collaboration, educators can enhance student understanding and retention of the material. Finally, the model concludes with the Evaluate and Revise step. This step involves ongoing evaluation of the instruction's effectiveness. Through assessments and feedback mechanisms, educators can identify areas for improvement and continuously refine the teaching and learning experience for future iterations. By following these steps, the ASSURE model empowers educators to create meaningful and engaging learning environments for students (Heinich, 2002; Smaldino, Lowther, & Russell, 2019).

3 Program Phases

In this section we describe the Design Sprint approach of the program proposed which has shown to be a phased approach to project success. The program is based on four main phases, with Phase 3 being the backbone of the program and learning as it applies the ASSURE model to engage future students (Erickson & Yorks, 2017). The Design Sprint methodology breaks the project development process into four distinct phases, each with its own focus and deliverables.

Phase 1: *Understand lays the foundation for the entire project.*

This phase is dedicated to gaining a deep understanding of the challenge at hand. By consulting with experts, the team gathers diverse perspectives and insights. Deliverables for this phase include a project management and planning report that outlines key milestones, and a comprehensive research report. This research combines secondary research, leveraging existing internal documentation of past experiences, with primary research, obtained by interviewing leaders from other organizations or universities to identify best practices.

Phase 2: *Monitor shifts the focus to the user and their specific needs.*

Here, the team conducts in-depth interviews with executives and facilitates a focus group to gather qualitative data. In addition, interviews with current internal leaders provide valuable insight into the skills required for their roles and any skill gaps within the team. This information culminates in qualitative and quantitative findings report.

Phase 3: *Think Up delves into the creative process of model development and program design.*

The team works together to configure a talent development model. This collaborative effort includes brainstorming sessions ("Ideation") to explore initial research and archetypes, followed by a period of "Divergence & Convergence" where ideas are expanded and ultimately refined into a cohesive program design. The final deliverable of this phase is a talent development model.

Phase 4: *Validate focuses on refining and finalizing the program approach.*

A focus group is convened to discuss the proposed program, and based on their feedback, the team prepares a final report and visual materials that effectively present the program. Finally, this phase concludes with a presentation to stakeholders that summarizes the project's findings and recommendations.

4 Talent Development Model

To put both the methodology and the phases into practice, the following proposal is considered. The strategy of using motivational phases for the Leadership Program is based on the idea that leaders seek to have a clear purpose in mind, which generally involves mastering or achieving certain knowledge in a field to later have the freedom and autonomy to use that knowledge to achieve their goals. For this reason, we propose the following axes for the program (Kouzes & Posner, 2017; Northouse, 2019):

- *Knowledge*: Strive to be better at everything you do, become an expert.
- *Purpose*: Everything you do has a personal and professional purpose and impact.
- *Autonomy*: Decide your own destiny and how you want to develop in life and career.

Based on these axes, we think about the background to follow the program, but the activities, and these are divided by type.

- *Baseline*: Throughout the program, participants will engage in various activities that follow a logical sequence. These activities will allow them to apply the knowledge and skills they have previously acquired.
- *Bonus*: Participants choose activities based on their preferences and aspirations. These activities earn points that can be exchanged for reward-type activities.
- *Reward*: Reward activities have a participant limit. Participants are selected based on the accumulation of bonus points and the submission of a request activity.

5 Training Path

In response to the company's requirements regarding talent development, the training path was designed to prioritize the three primary axes previously described: purpose, knowledge and autonomy; with activities tailored to specific types (Kouzes & Posner, 2017; Northouse, 2019).

5.1 Purpose

This program offers a three-month positive psychology course designed to equip managers as the company's "positive ambassadors." Through a series of modules, the course aims to establish a positive mindset within managers. Topics will delve into the foundations of positive psychology, exploring concepts such as overcoming adversity, goal setting, and fostering strong relationships with colleagues. The curriculum includes an introduction to positive psychology, followed by a deep dive into its various branches. Participants will learn practical techniques for positive transformation, including the power of positive feedback and strategies for maintaining overall well-being. By the conclusion of the program, managers will be equipped with the tools and knowledge to cultivate a positive and thriving work environment. This aspect of the "purpose" axis can be reinforced through various techniques, tools, and initiatives, including the following:

- ***Building Connections Through Film: Movie Night for Staff Integration***

Offers a unique opportunity to foster coexistence and learning among colleagues in a relaxed setting. This activity goes beyond simple entertainment by encouraging critical analysis of ethical issues presented in a film. The chosen movie will showcase a compelling narrative that confronts viewers with ethical dilemmas. Following the film, a structured discussion facilitated by a designated leader will guide participants through a case-study method. This method involves collaboratively analyzing the scenario in the film by:

- Identifying key facts and the core problems faced by the characters.
- Brainstorming potential solutions to these problems, weighing the advantages and disadvantages of each.
- Discussing the implementation of the chosen solution and its potential outcomes.

By openly discussing complex ethical dilemmas in the context of a shared cinematic experience, movie night facilitates learning and bonding among colleagues. Reflecting on the challenges and navigating solutions together fosters a sense of common understanding and strengthens team dynamics.

- ***Sharing Knowledge Across Locations: IntraForums***

Utilizes video conferencing technology to bridge the gap between geographically dispersed teams, promoting global corporate knowledge. These sessions connect teams from different company locations who share similar areas of expertise. The core objective is to share and enrich best practices, fostering a spirit of collaboration and continuous improvement.

During an IntraForum session, managers from different locations can present a current challenge they are facing within their teams. By sharing these real-world situations, colleagues can gain valuable insights into how similar situations are handled in other locations. This exchange allows for the dissemination of best practices, equipping participants with alternative approaches and solutions that may be applicable to their own teams.

To solidify the learning outcomes, the session concludes by highlighting the three most valuable takeaways identified during the discussion. These key points can then be implemented in each participating location, driving continuous improvement and knowledge sharing across the entire company.

5.2 Knowledge

The knowledge axis in the training path is designed to enhance the professional and technical skills of participants, preparing them to take on leadership roles and significantly contribute to innovation within the company. Through interactive workshops, immersions in high-tech environments, and programs that foster creativity and entrepreneurship, participants will acquire essential competencies that enable them to excel in their respective fields and adapt to the rapidly changing business landscape. The "knowledge" axis can be effectively developed through a range of activities and methodologies, such as the ones listed below:

- ***Building Your Brand and Voice: Personal Marketing and Public Speaking Workshop***

This comprehensive workshop equips participants with the skills and confidence to establish themselves as strong leaders and effective communicators. Targeting future leaders, the program focuses on honing personal branding and public speaking abilities. The workshop delves into the "6 Ps of personal marketing," a framework for building a strong individual brand. Participants will gain valuable insights into cultivating essential personal skills, including effective communication and interpersonal development. Mastering both verbal and non-verbal language is explored, empowering participants to deliver impactful messages.

Leadership development is fostered through engaging team games that identify individual leadership styles. Additionally, the workshop covers a range of practical skills, including public speaking techniques. Participants will receive impromptu speaking exercises, honing their ability to think on their feet and deliver clear, concise messages. Building on this foundation, sales techniques are explored through role-playing exercises, allowing participants to practice persuasive communication in a realistic setting.

The program also emphasizes the power of storytelling, equipping participants with the ability to craft and deliver impactful narratives. Networking strategies for building strong professional relationships are explored, preparing participants to navigate professional settings with confidence. To solidify the learning experience, the workshop culminates in a final presentation in the style of a TED Talk. This allows participants to showcase their newly acquired skills by delivering a 3–5-minute speech on a chosen topic, putting their personal brand and communication abilities on display.

- **Silicon Valley Immersion Tour: A Journey into Innovation**

The Silicon Valley Immersion Tour offers a unique opportunity for company leaders to delve into the heart of innovation. This immersive experience is specifically designed to connect participants with the latest trends and disruptive technologies shaping the industry. To participate, managers are invited to submit a one-minute video showcasing a project they envision implementing within the company. This selection process ensures that the learning experience aligns with individual and company goals.

The program itself is an immersive journey into the heart of Silicon Valley. Participants will have access to exclusive experiences, connecting with industry leaders, entrepreneurs, and thought provokers at the forefront of technological advancement. Following this intensive exposure to the cutting-edge, participants are given an additional five days to translate their learnings into actionable plans. During this structured period, they will define a clear strategy for leveraging the acquired knowledge to create positive impact within their company. By fostering firsthand exposure to the ever-evolving landscape of technology, the Silicon Valley Immersion Tour equips participants with the inspiration and tools to drive innovation and propel the company forward.

- **Igniting Intrapreneurship: Spin-Offs Program**

This program aims to unleash the entrepreneurial spirit within the company by fostering a culture of intrapreneurship. The Spin-Offs competition provides a platform for employees to showcase their creativity and develop innovative digital solutions. The program begins with the presentation of clearly defined challenges that the company seeks to address. Following this, teams are formed, uniting individuals with diverse skillsets and perspectives. These teams then embark on a collaborative journey, brainstorming, exploring, and ultimately developing solutions to the presented challenges. This collaborative process culminates in the creation of well-defined projects that address the needs of the company.

The final stage of the program involves a "pitch" session, where each team presents their proposed digital solution to a panel of judges. The three most compelling and well-executed projects are then awarded recognition. Selection criteria focus on the degree of project implementation, alignment with company strategy, and the innovative and disruptive nature of the proposed solution. By encouraging intrapreneurship and empowering employees to become innovators, the Spin-Offs program fosters a dynamic and creative environment, leading to the development of new digital solutions that contribute to the company's continued success.

5.3 Autonomy

The autonomy axis focuses on empowering participants to take control of their professional and personal development. Through immersive experiences and mutual learning programs, a comprehensive understanding of the company's operations is promoted, fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. This approach allows participants to develop a holistic business perspective, enhance their decision-making skills, and effectively contribute to the organization's strategic objectives. To foster autonomy, the program incorporates diverse strategies and practices, including but not limited to the following:

- **Fostering Professional Growth: "You Choose" Week.**

The "You Choose" Week program empowers participants to take charge of their professional development. By selecting a department, area, or business unit of interest, they gain firsthand experience for one week. This immersive experience broadens their knowledge base, fosters professional development, and provides a deeper understanding of the company's structure and strategy.

After choosing their area of interest, participants dive into a one-week rotation. This immersive experience allows them to shadow colleagues, observe workflows, and gain practical insights into daily operations. To maximize learning, participants will be actively involved in departmental activities and projects whenever

possible. To solidify their experience, participants will then engage in a self-reflection exercise prompted by specific questions to help them analyse their learnings.

- What did you learn in the area you rotated to? This prompts participants to identify key takeaways and knowledge gained during the rotation.
- What aspects of the area did you find most engaging? This question allows participants to identify areas of personal interest and potential career paths.
- What would you suggest improving the area's operations? This encourages participants to offer fresh perspectives and identify areas for potential optimization.

By actively participating in the "You Choose" Week program, postgraduate participants gain valuable insights into various aspects of the company, empowering them to make informed career decisions and contribute their talents to the area that best aligns with their professional aspirations.

- ***Expanding Expertise Through Inverse Shadowing***

The Inverse Shadowing program offers professionals a unique opportunity to gain a comprehensive understanding of the company's value chain. This program fosters a collaborative learning environment where participants can broaden their knowledge base and develop a holistic perspective of the company's operations. (Smith & Johnson, 2018; Brown, 2020).

The Inverse Shadowing program offers a unique twist on traditional shadowing. Participants gain a holistic view of the company by observing managers from various departments, but the learning goes both ways. Participants not only observe daily routines and decision-making, but also provide constructive feedback on the manager's communication, leadership, and potential areas for improvement. This reciprocal exchange fosters a collaborative learning environment where both parties gain valuable insights. Sessions are strategically planned to coincide with meetings or activities offering significant learning value, ensuring participants gain practical exposure to essential aspects of the manager's role. Ultimately, Inverse Shadowing empowers professionals with a global understanding of the company's value chain, leading to better decision-making and stronger collaboration across departments.

- ***Sharpen Your Social Edge: Building Emotional Intelligence for Managers***

This program provides managers with the emotional intelligence (EQ) skills needed to excel in social interactions. Through interactive workshops led by an EQ expert, participants gain insights into key EQ dimensions: self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, relationship management, and motivation. Real-world scenarios and case studies relevant to managers help them apply learned principles to daily situations, navigate complex interactions, and build stronger relationships. The program incorporates interaction with individuals both inside and outside the company, fostering a nuanced understanding of interpersonal dynamics. By enhancing their social intelligence, managers create a more positive work environment, motivate teams, and achieve superior performance.

6 Results

Evaluating the impact of a training program is not just a step in the employee development process, it's a crucial one. It's through this evaluation that organizations can adjust and modify content to meet their goals and needs. Reliable assessment of a program's results is essential. This is where training metrics, also known as training KPIs, step in. They are not just tools, but the key to gaining an accurate view of the effectiveness and success of training programs (Noe, 2016; Phillips & Phillips, 2017).

In this evaluation, we focused on a group of 30 students and used several key training indicators to measure their progress and engagement with the course. The first metric, completion rate, measures the percentage of students who complete a course or training program compared to the total number of students enrolled. This rate is an essential indicator of the effectiveness and commitment of the participants to the program. The formula for this training metric is as follows $\text{Completion Rate} = (\text{Number of Participants} / \text{Total Enrolled}) * 100$. For this group, the completion rate was calculated as $(27/30) * 100 = 90\%$. A high completion rate not only indicates strong participant engagement but also reassures you about the satisfaction of the participants with the course content and delivery. Conversely, a low completion rate may indicate problems with the relevance, difficulty, or accessibility of the course, and the need for additional support from the training team.

Attendance measures the percentage of scheduled training sessions that employees attend, providing crucial insight into their level of engagement and commitment. The formula for calculating this index is $\text{attendance rate} = (\text{attendees/sessions}) * 100$. For the group of 27 participants in 10 sessions, the total possible attendance was 270 (27 people x 10 sessions). The actual total attendance was 252, resulting in an attendance rate of $(252/270) * 100 \approx 93.33\%$. A high attendance rate is not just a number, it's a testament to the participants' active involvement and commitment to the training program. However, consistently low attendance may indicate scheduling conflicts, lack of interest, or dissatisfaction with the program, highlighting the need for further evaluation and improvement.

7 Conclusion

Training indicators or metrics are essential for evaluating training programs' success and impact. They provide concrete data that enables professionals, trainers, and employees to understand the effectiveness of their training efforts. The data provided by training metrics is not just numbers, they are the reassurance that your investments in training are justified. This ensures that training programs deliver appropriate performance and value to the organization, making you feel more confident in your training investments. Training metrics enable organizations to measure the performance of individuals and teams before, during, and after training. By assessing skill development, knowledge retention, and behavior change, managers can determine the impact of training on job performance.

Training metrics provide valuable feedback that supports continuous improvement efforts. Organizations can analyze trends, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and implement targeted interventions to enhance training strategies and maximize their effectiveness. By using training metrics, organizations can optimize resource allocation. This includes prioritizing initiatives that deliver the highest return on investment and ensuring the efficient use of time, money, and effort to support strategic priorities while keeping costs stable. In industries with stringent regulatory requirements, training metrics are not just numbers, they are the security blanket that ensures your employees are receiving the necessary compliance training. Tracking completion rates, quality control, and mastery of compliance training helps organizations mitigate risk and avoid costly penalties, making you feel more at ease with compliance training.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial and technical support of Writing Lab, Institute for the Future of Education, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico, in the production of this work.

8 References

- Brown, C. (2020). Collaborative learning in professional development. Learning Press.
- Bruner, J. (1996). The culture of education.

- Erickson, T., & Yorks, L. (2017). *The project management scorecard: Measuring the success of project management solutions*. Routledge.
- Heinich, R. M. (2002). *Instructional media and technologies for learning* (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Johnson, B. (2018). *Understanding corporate value chains: A comprehensive guide*. Business Publishing.
- Knowles, M. S. (1984). *The adult learner: A neglected species*.
- Kouzes, J. M., & Posner, B. Z. (2017). *The leadership challenge: How to make extraordinary things happen in organizations* (6th ed.). Wiley.
- Merriam, S. B., & Bierema, L. L. (2014). *Adult learning: Linking theory and practice*.
- Morrison, G. R., Ross, S. J., Morrison, J. R., & Kalman, H. K. (2013). *Designing effective instruction*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Noe, R. A. (2016). *Employee training and development* (7th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Northouse, P. G. (2019). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (8th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Phillips, J. J., & Phillips, P. P. (2017). *Measuring the success of learning through technology* (2nd ed.). ATD Press.
- Smaldino, S. E., Lowther, D. L., & Russell, J. D. (2019). *Instructional technology and media for learning* (12th ed.). Pearson.
- Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2018). *Understanding corporate value chains: A comprehensive guide*. Business Publishing.